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PhD 16 - Codes4strain

Responsible Partner: Institut Pasteur

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Comparison of the ANI metric with the cgMLST metric

We compared ANI-based distances with the number of mismatches between cgMLST profiles (**Figure 1**). While the ANI-based distances varied from 92.8% to 100%, the cgMLST distances varied from 0 to 100% (*i.e.*, 629 allele mismatches). Although both distributions had four to five modes, the first two modes of the ANI distance distribution, composed of inter-phylogroup strain comparisons, were at 93.5% to 95.5% ANI, whereas in the cgMLST distribution these distance pairs were centered around 2%, corresponding to the first mode of this distribution. In turn, whereas intra-species cgMLST distances varied from 5% to 100%, the range was only 98% to 100% for ANI values.

Figure 1. The distribution of pairwise distances of 7060 genomes of Kp based on Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) and cgMLST.

(A) Each point represents a pair of distances between two strains, the X-axis the distance cgMLST and the Y-axis the distance ANI, the distributions are shown on the outside of the graph. We have colored the points corresponding to intergroup and intragroup distance. (B) Distribution of cgMLST pairwise distance. (C) Distribution of ANI pairwise distance.

The ANI metric was not designed to define the similarity of closely related genomes, such as those of strains within species; for example, high similarity values (e.g. 99.9990% and 99.9991%) are not intuitive to compare. In addition, the ANI metric is non-reciprocal, is highly dependent on comparison parameters, and is sensitive to sequencing or assembly artifacts. This shortfalls of the ANI metric lead to imprecision and non-reproducibility that are particularly impactful for comparisons between very similar genomes. In contrast, the metric based on a cgMLST scheme, comprising 629 highly conserved and syntenic genes, was appropriate to reveal discontinuities that are relevant for strain nomenclature purposes.

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References:

A dual barcoding approach to bacterial strain nomenclature: Genomic taxonomy of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains. Melanie Hennart, Julien Guglielmini, Martin C.J. Maiden, Keith A. Jolley, Alexis Criscuolo, Sylvain Brisse. bioRxiv 2021.07.26.453808; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.07.26.453808>